

DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND PRODUCTION VOLUME FORECAST OF THE GARMENT AND TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. *This article examines the ways in which textile enterprises of the Samarkand region can increase their position in the republican and international markets, for which the analysis of marketing activities at enterprises and the application of new methods, approaches and mechanisms are used, and the analysis of yarn products as part of import operations of textile and knitted and garment products is considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, international market, mechanism, knitted and garment products, import, operation, analysis.*

Introduction. The textile and garment and knitwear industry is one of the fastest growing industries in the world. The global textile and clothing market was valued at \$1,695.23 billion in 2024. It is projected to grow at a CAGR of 7.7% through 2030.

The experience of countries with a developed textile industry shows that, under favorable conditions created by the state, the development of the textile industry can become a turning point for the economic growth of the country and its regions. The policies pursued in China and India are a clear example of this.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan as a result of the implementation of comprehensive measures to develop the textile and garment and knitwear industry, support the investment and export activities of enterprises in the sector, the production volume in 2024 amounted to 123.21 trillion soums, and the annual export potential of the sector reached \$2.9 billion.

Analysis of literature on the topic While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include I. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, A. Sh. Bekmurodov, A. A. Fattakhov, M. R. Boltaboev, S. J. Ergashkhodjaeva and M. Kosimova, M. I. Ikramov, S. A. Musaeva, G. Sh. Khankeldieva, M. M. Akbarov, S. A. Abdullaeva and others.

The research and scientific results carried out by scientists have created the scientific and methodological foundations of marketing activities in the textile industry, however, the globalization of the textile and clothing market, the entry of new large players and the creation of new methods of competition create new dangers and risks for the textile industry of Uzbekistan. Therefore, improving the methodology of marketing activities to ensure competitiveness in the domestic and foreign markets is becoming an urgent problem.

Research methodology. The research process used a systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation methods.

Analysis and results. To analyze the role of the textile and garment industry in the Samarkand region, it is necessary to first pay attention to statistical data. Textile and clothing production is one of the important areas of the industry.

Today, regional statistical data allows for an analysis of this industry in two areas: textile production and clothing production (Table 1).

Table 1.

Dynamics of textile and clothing production in Samarkand region in 2017-2024¹

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	8870.5	12941.7	15130.6	17396.2	21744.8	27963.5	31739.9	44786.7
Textile production	1764.7	2156.5	2166.9	3637.6	4390.0	5132.8	5809.7	7646.8
Clothing production	224.9	341.7	271.3	597.1	657.6	697.1	815.8	1206.8
Total textile and clothing production	1989.6	2498.2	2438.2	4234.7	5047.6	5829.9	6625.5	8853.6
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

As can be seen from the data in this table, the textile and garment and knitwear industry of the region has been developing rapidly in 2017-2024. If in 2017 a total of 8870.5 billion soums worth of products were produced, by 2024 this figure reached 44786.7 billion soums, that is, it has increased fivefold. The object of our study, textile and clothing production, which was the subject of our study, in 2017 a total of 1989.6 billion soums worth of products were created, increased to 8853.6 billion soums in 2024, that is, the growth was 4.45 times. From this, it can be concluded that other areas of the manufacturing industry are developing faster than the textile and clothing industry.

At the same time, this sector remains one of the main elements of the manufacturing industry (Table 2.)

2.- table

The share of textile and clothing production in the manufacturing industry in the region in 2017-2024 (in%)

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	100.0							
Textile production	19.9	16.7	14.3	20.9	20.2	18.4	18.3	17.1
Clothing production	2.5	2.6	1.8	3.4	3.0	2.5	2.6	2.7

¹Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Total textile and clothing production	22.4	19.3	16.1	24.3	23.2	20.9	20.9	19.8
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One fifth of the manufacturing industry is made up of textiles and clothing, which means that this sector constitutes a significant part of the industry. In recent years, we can observe a decrease in the share of the textile industry. In 2017 While textile and clothing manufacturing accounted for 22.4% of the manufacturing industry, this figure decreased to 19.8% in 2024.

If we analyze the patterns in textile and clothing production in the Samarkand region, we can see that there is a stable growth trend in the industry in 2010-2024. Based on this pattern, it is possible to draw up a production forecast for 2025-2030 using the exponential correction method.

Exponential Smoothing is a time series forecasting method in which the importance of new observations (numbers in the last years of the period) is higher than that of older observations. The formula for a simple exponential smoothing is:

$$St = \alpha * Yt + (1 - \alpha) * St-1$$

Where: Yt is the actual number of rows;

St – the corrected number in the t-th period of the series;

α – correction coefficient ($0 < \alpha < 1$). If α approaches zero, the forecast takes into account more previous data, on the contrary, if it approaches one, the forecast considers the latest data to be extremely important. Taking into account the deep reforms in our country in recent years, we took the α -coefficient equal to 0.8 (Table 2.3). To carry out the forecast, we used data on production volumes by types of economic activity in the Samarkand region for 2010-2024².

Another method of forecasting economic series is Holt's Linear Trend Method, which combines the exponential correction of time series with the addition of a trend. This method combines two actions, namely, adjusting the current values of the series and adjusting the direction and magnitude of the series' change. The general forecast formula is then:

$$\hat{Y}_{t+h} = Lt + h * Tt$$

Where: Lt is the grade of the level;

Tt - trend estimate;

h is the forecast period.

The forecast made according to the Holt method is considered somewhat more accurate, since it takes into account the reforms taking place in our country. If we perform the calculations using the above data, we obtain the following results (Table 3).

Table 3.

Forecast of textile and clothing production volumes in Samarkand region using exponential correction and Holt method, billion soums.

Years	Exponential correction method	Holt method
2025	9722,818	9715,989
2026	11175,339	11167,629

²Open data of the Samarkand regional department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

(https://samstat.uz/uz/?preview=1&option=com_dropfiles&format=&task=frontfile.download&catid=286&id=5805&Itemid=1000000000000)

2027	12627,860	12619,269
2028	14080,382	14070,909
2029	15532,903	15522,549
2030	16985,424	16974,189

The closeness of the forecasts in the table indicates that the calculations performed correspond to the current trends and trend lines. Based on this, it can be assumed with a high probability that the volume of textile and garment and knitwear production in Samarkand region in 2030 will reach 16,980 billion soums.

In the production of textile and clothing products, along with general economic indicators, indicators in physical volumes are of great economic and social importance (tons, sq. m., pieces, pairs, etc.). To continue the analysis of textile and clothing production, we tracked the physical changes in product production in the manufacturing industry (Table 4)

Table 4.
Change in the physical volume index of industrial production in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent³

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	124.3	112.4	106.0	105.4	112.5	109.3	106.5	108.4
Textile production	120.4	95.4	95.9	135.6	96.7	92.6	110.0	103.9
Clothing production	120.9	152.3	85.5	80.1	101.0	94.6	106.1	110.9

From the data in this table, it can be seen that the physical volume of total industrial production in the region has been steadily growing in 2017-2024. The average annual growth rate was at least 105.4 percent (in 2020), and the largest increase was 124.3 percent (in 2017). As for textile products, we can see a decrease in physical volume in most years of the observed period. The physical volumes of clothing production have also changed unevenly, that is, while a significant increase was observed in 2017 and 2018, there was a decrease in 2019, 2020 and 2022 compared to the previous year. Starting from 2023, the volume of production has changed in line with the growth trend. An analysis of the physical volumes of product production shows a large number of unused reserves at the enterprises of the region.

The place of the textile and garment industry in the economy of the region can be assessed by its role in foreign economic activity. The production of textile and garment products constitutes the main part of the export potential of the region. A total of 14 types of textile and garment products are included in the foreign economic activity of the region (Table 5).

³Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Table 5.

Export indicators of textile and garment and knitwear products in Samarkand region

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Silk	875	6,962.60	10,556.10	12,026.80	13,609.30	17,513.40	15,661.70	11,319.40
Wool and wool yarn	269.9	0	0	0	0	46.8	0	0
Cotton	9 345.00	3,504.10	14,884.80	28 270.90	63,854.60	63,085.20	30 277.10	33,545.80
Other vegetable textile fibers	0	0	0	0	70.8	41.4	178.5	51.9
Chemical yarns	1 561.30	496.6	1 282.60	1 334.00	3,775.60	1 510.60	1 349.80	2 153.50
Chemical fiber	3,435.10	2 475.20	4 771.90	4 401.10	9 105.30	10,532.90	5 861.90	10 125.10
Other non-woven products	234.9	586.3	323.5	213.1	229.5	405	151.4	561.5
Total yarn	15721.2	14024.8	31818.9	46245.9	90645.1	93135.3	53480.4	57757.2
Carpets and other floor coverings	32422.90	29014.00	29811.10	27532.20	32223.60	23763.00	21185.20	21010.50
Total carpets	32422.9	29014.0	29811.1	27532.2	32223.6	23763.0	21185.2	21010.5
Special fabrics and trims	74.9	0	23.96	218	1,007.20	1,083.80	272.3	568
Textile products for technical purposes	0	0	98.9	178.8	262.1	12.7	28.8	87.3
Knitted fabrics	7.25	0.13	35.37	2 157.80	10 103.40	8,813.10	6 156.40	3,960.60

Total fabrics	82.15	0.13	158.23	2554.6	11372.7	9909.6	6457.5	4615.9
Knitted clothing products	10938.70	16589.8	20414.6	17187.00	24982.20	31097.20	37816.30	23077.4
Clothing products (except knitwear)	3829.50	4 684.00	4148.0	3,424.50	6,539.10	10,066.50	7,932.60	6149.20
Total clothing items	14768.2	21273.8	24562.6	20611.5	31521.3	41163.7	45748.9	29226.6
Other finished textile products	372.3	260.6	1,522.50	2,544.40	5,542.10	6 678.50	7 671.60	8832.5
Total	63366.75	64573.33	87873.33	99488.6	171304.8	174650.1	134543.6	121442.7

From the data in this table, it can be seen that the export indicators of textile and garment and knitwear products are not stable during the observed period. In particular, we can see that the situation with exports deteriorated in 2023-2024. The diagram below clearly demonstrates this situation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Changes in exports of textile and garment and knitwear products in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, billion soums.

To analyze the export of textiles and clothing, we combined these fourteen product types included in the foreign economic commodity nomenclature into groups: yarn, carpets, fabrics, ready-made garments, and other finished textile products (Table 6).

Table 6.

Structure of textile and knitwear exports in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent⁴

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total yarn	25	22	36	46	53	53	40	48
Total carpets	51	45	34	28	19	14	16	17
Total fabrics	0	0	0	3	7	6	5	4
Total ready-made clothing products	23	33	28	21	18	24	34	24
Other finished textile products	1	0	2	3	3	4	6	7
Total	100							

From this table, we can see that during the observed period, the share of yarn and thread products in the export of textile and knitwear products increased (from 25% in 2017 to 48% in 2024), that is, we do not consider the shift of exports towards raw materials to be a positive situation. Of particular note is the sharp decrease in the share of carpet exports. At the same time, an increase in the export of fabrics and other finished textile products is observed.

We analyzed the share of textile and sewing and knitwear products in the import operations of the Samarkand region (Table 2).

Table 6

Import indicators of textile and sewing and knitted products in Samarkand region⁵

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Yarn	28714.1	44946.2	44630.5	36727.2	44783.1	54454.4	68376.8	72483.3
Carpets	1.5	4.6	1.2	6.6	71.1	439	875.3	515.7
Fabrics	4,645.0	5,832.5	6,869.6	6891.8	9 226.1	12,095.2	16,332.4	13,053.3
Ready-made clothing products	433.5	1423.7	419.8	51.1	59.8	219.5	353.6	323.2
Other finished textile products	251.9	112.3	174.2	132.8	164	430.8	246.8	260.3
Total	34046.0	52319.3	52095.3	43809.5	54304.1	67638.9	86184.9	86635.8

⁴Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁵Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In the structure of import operations of textile and knitwear and clothing products in Samarkand region, yarn and thread products occupy the main place (84.3% in 2017 and 83.6% in 2024). In second place is the import of fabrics, which accounted for 13.6% and 15.1% of imports, respectively. It can be concluded that the textile and knitwear and clothing industry of Samarkand region has a positive foreign economic balance, that is, the share of finished products in imports is very low (Table 2).

Table 7.

Structure of imports of textile and knitwear products in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Yarn	84.3	85.8	85.6	83.3	82.5	80.5	79.3	83.6
Carpets	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.6	1.0	0.6
Fabrics	13.6	11.1	13.2	15.6	17.0	17.9	18.9	15.1
Clothing products	1.3	2.7	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.4
Other finished textile products	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.6	0.3	0.3
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

To estimate the level of net exports, we add up the obtained figures. We compared this with the volume of textile and clothing exports. (Figure 5). From this diagram, it can be seen that the excess of textile and clothing exports over imports exceeded 66% in 2020, and by 2024 it had decreased to 34.7%.

Figure 4. Data on net exports of textiles and clothing in Samarkand region

We attribute this to increased activity in traditional markets and the discovery of new ones during the coronavirus pandemic. We believe that the decline in net exports in recent years is due to increased competition in the global and domestic textile markets and the opening up of the Uzbek economy. In order to provide a complete analysis of the export of the textile and garment and

knitwear industry in the region, we determine the ratio of net exports to the volume of exports of products. (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Ratio of net exports of textile and clothing products in Samarkand region to the total export volume of the region, in percent.

Based on the data in this diagram, in recent years, a downward trend has been observed in the change in net exports of textile products of the region. This indicator was 33.49 percent in 2023, and 26.26 percent in 2024. It can be concluded that the textile enterprises of the region need to increase their position in the republican and international markets. For this, it is advisable to analyze marketing activities at enterprises and apply best practices in applying new methods, approaches and mechanisms in it.

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